

IMPACT RESPONSE OF HEATED MULTILAYERED COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The thermoelastic problem of low velocity impact of a rigid body on a multilayered orthotropic plate is considered. For the solution of the thermoelastic problem the displacement spline approximation method, developed in [1-3] was extended. To verify the theoretical formulation and computer code, a static free edge boundary value problem in a five layered composite plate was considered. The transverse stresses arising in the vicinity of the free edge due to a temperature change were compared to those obtained by using the ASCA computer code based upon the theory developed in [4-6]. The stress analysis in the multilayered composite plate under impact loading is performed. The interlaminar stress wave propagation is demonstrated for a $[0^0/90^0]_s$ laminate.

1. INTRODUCTION

The application of the multilayered composite materials in high performance structures requires the development of efficient methods of analysis. The complexity of this problem is due to the necessity to obtain the detailed stress-strain characteristics at the interlaminar surfaces and on the fiber-matrix level. Considering the problem of transverse impact on the composite structure with characteristic loading times of 10^{-3} sec the quantitative understanding of interlaminar transverse shear and normal stresses is of great importance. To calculate the accurate interlaminar stresses, the jump of the transverse strain components at the interfaces used to be accounted for. Three-dimensional solid finite element procedures are capable of

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calculating a detailed stress field when a sufficient number of elements are used. However a three-dimensional analysis poses practical problems in terms of computer memory usage and computational time requirements. It is worth mentioning that the practical composite structures may consist of up to a hundred plies and several elements through the thickness of each ply (layer). They are needed to obtain the interlaminar stresses within the 5-10% accuracy. The displacement plate and shell finite element procedures are based on averaging the inhomogeneous properties through the thickness and violating the interface traction conditions. In this case the multilayered structure is actually replaced by a homogeneous anisotropic and the calculation of accurate interfacial stresses is impossible.

A method based on spline approximations of displacements and developed in [1-3] for dynamic elastic problems is extended to account for the temperature effects. The displacement spline approximation provides the continuity of displacements and strains in the plate except transverse strain components at the interfaces between different layers. The jump of this strain component allows to achieve the continuity of transverse stresses on the interlaminar surfaces with a prescribed accuracy. The interlaminar shear and normal stresses obtained by use of the present method were compared to those obtained by use of the interface functions developed in [4-6] and implemented in the ASCA computer code. An excellent agreement of results in the thermoelastic free edge boundary value problem for two approaches was observed.

Interlaminar stress history in multilayered composite plates under low velocity impact loading was studied. Free edge boundary conditions were imposed considering one point support at the edge. A zone of intensive tensile transverse normal stresses at the interlaminar interface arising at the free edge was observed.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Figure 1 shows the coordinate axis and applied loading in a composite plate. A rectangular plate of length L in the x -direction, width A in the y -direction and thickness H is considered and is located in $oxyz$ coordinates to occupy the region $[0,L]*[0,A]*[0,H]$. The plate consists of n orthotropic layers. In each layer the orientation of principal material axes x_1, x_2, x_3 is defined relative to the x -axis and the ply angle denoted by $\theta_k, k=1, \dots, n$ is counted clockwise in xy plane. Linear theory of elasticity has been considered. In the k^{th} layer of the laminate, the stress-strain relations can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{xx}^{(k)} &= \bar{Q}_{11}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xx} + \bar{Q}_{12}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{yy} + \bar{Q}_{13}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{zz} + \bar{Q}_{16}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xy} - \bar{S}_1^{(k)}, \\
\sigma_{yy}^{(k)} &= \bar{Q}_{21}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xx} + \bar{Q}_{22}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{yy} + \bar{Q}_{23}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{zz} + \bar{Q}_{26}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xy} - \bar{S}_2^{(k)}, \\
\sigma_{zz}^{(k)} &= \bar{Q}_{31}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xx} + \bar{Q}_{32}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{yy} + \bar{Q}_{33}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{zz} + \bar{Q}_{36}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xy} - \bar{S}_3^{(k)}, \\
\sigma_{yz}^{(k)} &= \bar{Q}_{44}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{yz} + \bar{Q}_{45}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xz}, \\
\sigma_{xz}^{(k)} &= \bar{Q}_{54}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{yz} + \bar{Q}_{55}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xz}, \\
\sigma_{xy}^{(k)} &= \bar{Q}_{61}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xx} + \bar{Q}_{62}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{yy} + \bar{Q}_{63}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{zz} + \bar{Q}_{66}^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xy} - \bar{S}_6^{(k)}.
\end{aligned}$$

The $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)}$ are the k^{th} layer stiffness transformed to $oxyz$ coordinates. Temperature stress terms can be calculated as follows :

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{S}_1^{(k)} &= (\bar{Q}_{11}^{(k)} \alpha_{xx}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{12}^{(k)} \alpha_{yy}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{13}^{(k)} \alpha_{zz}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{16}^{(k)} \alpha_{xy}^{(k)}) \Delta T(x, y, z), \\
\bar{S}_2^{(k)} &= (\bar{Q}_{21}^{(k)} \alpha_{xx}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{22}^{(k)} \alpha_{yy}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{23}^{(k)} \alpha_{zz}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{26}^{(k)} \alpha_{xy}^{(k)}) \Delta T(x, y, z), \\
\bar{S}_3^{(k)} &= (\bar{Q}_{31}^{(k)} \alpha_{xx}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{32}^{(k)} \alpha_{yy}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{33}^{(k)} \alpha_{zz}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{36}^{(k)} \alpha_{xy}^{(k)}) \Delta T(x, y, z), \\
\bar{S}_6^{(k)} &= (\bar{Q}_{61}^{(k)} \alpha_{xx}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{62}^{(k)} \alpha_{yy}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{63}^{(k)} \alpha_{zz}^{(k)} + \bar{Q}_{66}^{(k)} \alpha_{xy}^{(k)}) \Delta T(x, y, z),
\end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha_{xx}^{(k)}, \alpha_{yy}^{(k)}, \alpha_{zz}^{(k)}, \alpha_{xy}^{(k)}$ are the thermal expansion coefficients in the k^{th} layer transformed to $oxyz$ coordinates. The temperature change $\Delta T(x, y, z)$ is considered to be uniform throughout the plate and predetermined. The Lagrange function of the plate can be presented in the form

$$E = K - \Pi + \Pi_T + A$$

where K - is the kinetic energy of the plate , $\Pi - \Pi_T$ is the potential energy and A is the external load work . The temperature dependent term in the potential energy expressions is as follows:

$$\Pi_T = \int_0^H \int_0^A \int_0^L (\bar{S}_1^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xx} + \bar{S}_2^{(k)} \varepsilon_{yy} + \bar{S}_3^{(k)} \varepsilon_{zz} + \bar{S}_6^{(k)} \varepsilon_{xy}) dx dy dz \quad (1)$$

The normal transverse load is applied to the top surface $z=H, \sigma_{zz}(x, y, H, t) = -q(x, y, t)$ so that

$$A = \int_0^H \int_0^L q(x, y, t) u_z(x, y, H, t) dx dy. \quad (2)$$

Let us consider term (1) . Integrating by parts can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_T = & \int_0^H dz \int_0^A [\bar{S}_1^{(k)}(u_x(L,y,z,t) - u_x(0,y,z,t)) + \bar{S}_6^{(k)}(u_y(L,y,z,t) - u_y(0,y,z,t))] dy + \\ & + \int_0^H dz \int_0^L [\bar{S}_2^{(k)}(u_y(x,A,z,t) - u_y(x,0,z,t)) + \bar{S}_6^{(k)}(u_x(x,A,z,t) - u_x(x,0,z,t))] dx + \\ & + \int_0^A dy \int_0^L \{ \bar{S}_3^{(n)} u_z(x,y,H,t) - \bar{S}_3^{(1)} u_z(x,y,0,t) - \sum_{s=1}^{n-1} [\bar{S}_3^{(s+1)} - \bar{S}_3^{(s)}] u_z(x,y,z_{I_s},t) \} dx, \end{aligned}$$

were $z_{I_s}, s=1, \dots, n-1$ are the coordinates of interfaces between $s+1$ and s layers

$$z_{I_s} = \sum_{i=1}^s h_i, \quad z_{I_0} = 0, \quad z_{I_n} = H.$$

The thermal expansion terms are now represented in the form similar to (2) and can be considered as an effective load acting on the plate surfaces and interfaces between different layers. The set of equations for calculation of the unknown displacements is obtained from the condition

$$\delta \int_0^t E dt = 0$$

The external load $q(x,y,t)$ applied to the facial surface $z=H$ can be either prescribed as a certain pressure pulse and determined by an amplitude versus time relation or calculated along with the plate deformation characteristics in the case of impact loading. The two dimensional dynamic contact problem describing the impact interaction based on displacements spline approximation was discussed in [3].

3. METHOD OF SOLUTION

The polynomial spline functions are used for displacement approximation. The following properties of the displacement field in the multilayered structure are necessary to account for :

- (a) Displacement components are continuous every where within the plate
- (b) At least the first partial derivative of the displacement components are continuous except for the one with respect to transverse coordinate at ply interfaces producing a jump in transverse strains at the interface.

These conditions are necessary but not sufficient to exactly satisfy traction continuity conditions at the interfaces.

To introduce the three dimensional spline approximation of the required parameters, three sets of nodal points in z , x and y directions are specified. Each layer is divided into l_k , $k=1, \dots, n$

sublayers with interfaces $z=z_i$, where $0 < z_1 < \dots < z_N = H$ ($N = \sum_{i=1}^n l_i$ - total number of sublayers). The length and width of the zone are divided into intervals $0 < x_1 < \dots < x_M = L$ and

$0 < y_1 < \dots < y_K = A$ respectively. The displacement spline approximation can be written as

$$u_\alpha = \sum_{s=1} S_s U_{\alpha s}(t), \quad \alpha = x, y, z,$$

The three dimensional spline approximation functions are

$$S_s = \chi_{m_1, j}(x) \chi_{m_2, k}(y) Z_{m_3, i}(z), \quad s = (j-1)N_z K_y + (k-1)N_z + i$$

where $\{\chi_{m_1, j}(x)\}_{j=1}^{M_x}$, $\{\chi_{m_2, k}(y)\}_{k=1}^{K_y}$, $\{Z_{m_3, i}(z)\}_{i=1}^{N_z}$ are sets of linearly independent spline functions of order m_1 , m_2 , m_3 , respectively. The spline functions $Z_{m_3, i}(z)$ used for displacement approximation in the direction normal to the interfaces between different layers provide the conditions (a) and (b) having zero multiplicity nodes inside the layers and m_3-1 multiplicity nodes at the interfaces between layers as described in [3].

NUMERICAL RESULTS

For validating the computer code and the theory developed for this investigation a comparative study was done. The free edge problem in a five layered plate was considered. The plate consists of three graphite/epoxy unidirectional layers and soft interleaves in between. The following material constants are used for the graphite/epoxy layer:

$$E_{11} = 172 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_{33} = E_{22} = 7 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{13} = G_{21} = 3.5 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{23} = 1.4 \text{ GPa},$$

$$\nu_{13} = \nu_{21} = 0.25, \quad \alpha_{11} = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-8}, \quad \alpha_{22} = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}; \quad \Delta T = 500^\circ\text{C};$$

and for the isotropic interleaves $E=0.7 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.25$, $\alpha = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$. The layer thicknesses in symmetric layout $[0^\circ, \text{IN}, 90^\circ, \text{IN}, 0^\circ]$ are chosen to be 3.3/1/3.3/1/3.3 mm. The transverse shear and normal stress distribution through the thickness was calculated. Using the present model each layer was divided into 6 sublayers and 55 intervals in x-direction. Calculation based upon the model [4-6] were made using the ASCA computer code [7] developed at AdTech Systems Research Inc. The transverse shear σ_{xz} given in Fig. 2 and normal σ_{zz} given in Fig. 3 obtained by two models are very close. The values of transverse normal stresses on the free edge (Fig. 3.a) at the interface has a slight disagreement between two cases. However, the results are expected to show such disagreement in view of the material discontinuity.

The onset of failure in composite plates due to low velocity impact was analyzed in [2,3]. It was shown that in a certain range of the impactor velocity the transverse shear stresses exceed

the ultimate values in a local area in the vicinity of the impact zone. Other stress components are relatively smaller compared to their ultimate values. The characteristic time when the maximum shear stresses were observed was twice the time duration of stress wave propagation through the thickness of the plate. The purpose of the present study is to consider the inplane propagation of the stress waves and to perform the analysis for considerably larger time scale (several times of stress wave propagation through the length of the plate).

The interlaminar stress analysis of a cross ply AS4/3501 laminate subjected to transverse impact by a rigid sphere was performed. The two dimensional x, z-plane problem was considered. A point support boundary conditions on the $x=0,L$ edges was imposed, i.e.

$$u_z(0,0,t) = u_z(0,L,t) = 0$$

At the rest of the lateral surface, traction free boundary conditions were considered. The following values of the physical parameters were used:

length of the plate $L=0.075\text{m}$,

layer thickness $h_1=h_2=h_3=2\text{mm}$,

$[0^0/90^0/0^0]$ - layup;

impact energy 4,5 J, velocity of the impactor $v=40\text{ m/sec}$.

The characteristic time of the stress wave propagation through the length of the plate can be calculated using the following parameter:

$$\tilde{t} = L / \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n Q_{11}^{(k)} h_k / \sum_{k=1}^n \rho^{(k)} h_k}$$

In this case $\tilde{t} = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{ sec}$.

The interlaminar stress wave propagation is demonstrated in Fig.4. Transverse normal stress σ_{zz} and shear stress σ_{xz} distribution upon x-coordinate are plotted at the interface between bottom and middle layers. Maximum shear and tensile normal stress values are indicated at $t=0.54t$ in the vicinity of the impact zone. The high tensile normal stresses are stimulated due to the decompression wave reflected from the bottom free surface of the plate. At that time, high stresses are concentrated in a local zone about $0.1L$ away from the center of the plate where the delamination is most likely to start. The stress wave propagation analysis shows that the problem of locating the possible damage zone becomes very difficult. The zone of high interlaminar shear stresses is through the length with only a small loss of amplitude (Fig.4.a). Also, another critical zone of extremely high normal tensile stresses has developed near the free edge due to the inertia effect thereby causing a pull out of the plate from the supports.

REFERENCES

1. A. E. Bogdanovich and E.V.Yarve, Proceedings of the American Society for Composites, Fourth Technical Conference, 399 (1989)
2. A. E. Bogdanovich, E.V.Iarve and S.P. Joshi, In Impact and Buckling of Structures, Proceedings of ASME, AD 20, 1 (1990)
3. A. E. Bogdanovich and E.V.Yarve, Mechanics of Composite Materials (in Russian, translated by Consultant Bureau, New York, Plenum Publishing Corporation), 5, 804 (1980)
4. N.J. Pagano, Int.J.Solids & Struct., 14, 385 (1978)
5. N.J. Pagano, Int.J.Solids & Struct., 14, 401 (1978)
6. N.J. Pagano and S.R. Soni, Int.J.Solids & Struct., 19, 385 (1978)
7. AdTech Systems Research Inc., "ASCA : The Automated System for Composite Analysis", developed under a cooperative program with Air Force Materials Laboratory.

FIGURE 1. Coordinate axis and applied loading to composite plate

FIGURE 2. Transverse shear σ_{xz} stress at $x=0.1L$, $\Delta T=50^\circ\text{C}$. D - present model, G - ASCA.

FIGURE 3. Transverse normal σ_{zz} stress at $x=0$ (a), $x=0.1L$ (b), $\Delta T=50^\circ\text{C}$. F,C - present model; H,I - ASCA.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 4. Interlaminar σ_{xz} - (a) and σ_{zz} - (b) stresses for different time instances